

“Go Green Model” – A Study on HRM Practices in NLC India Ltd, Neyveli

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Abstract : *The present research paper emphasis on ‘Go Green’ concept application in Human Resource Management in Neyveli Lignite Corporation (NLC) India Ltd. Neyveli. It is significant and need of the hour that public enterprise with the status of ‘Navaratna’ has come under the umbrella of Technology Inclusion system in all its functions to rationalize their organizational growth and development through employee efficiency and up skill practices in their operations. In this context the study made an analysis of select HRM practices through Green Technology and the study is descriptive in nature. Data collected on both sources, primary and secondary. The sample population was chosen on snowball sampling method. The size of sample is 915 and data collected through well-structured Interview Schedule The interview schedule was used different sample size of each category employee worked in the study organization. Finally, the study concluded that the firm strictly following of Go Green practices in all aspects, as a result, employees demonstrate green behaviour leading to green organizational outcomes. At the corporate level, the firm benefits from cost advantages and improve financial performance. The firm’s also enjoy a positive brand image of a green employer, attract talented worker, create a green culture environment and achieve their sustainability goals. If the above steps are followed correctly, there is no doubt that NLC India Neyveli will be the leading company in the world in the future.*

Keywords : Go Green, Employee Performance, Human Resource Management. Organization, Worker and Environment.

Introduction

Human Resource Management (HRM) is a pivotal factor and fixed continuous phenomenon in business management. Each and every organization emphasis more attention on this element, due to it, working and operating aspect in all of its activities. Hence it is called a human capital for every enterprise to accomplish its desire course of alternatives. Due to transformation of technology the organization strives to maximise the output, increase employees efficiency and apply digital and scientific way of performance. In this present scenario, the organization is coming forward to function of human resource through ‘Go Green’ model.

Review from Earlier Studies

Paula Benevene * and Ilaria Buonomo (2020) this research study emphasis on greening the organization through human resource and move forward for greater effectiveness and organizational development.

José F. Molina-Azorin (2021) it emphasis on environmental and eco system importance and found that organization lead high growth in productivity with exercise of green technology. In this context, the study takes into relationship on environmental strategy and green human resources policy and practices.

Prakash Chandra Bahuguna (2022) it enforces on sustainability through Green human resource practices and emphasis on green work environment in the organization for improving morale and high productivity.

Identification of the Research Gap

‘Go Green’ model practices different ways in varying different levels of analysis through considering engagement motivation and job satisfaction. As an evident from the many earlier and recent studies conducted which have recognized by engagement, motivation and job satisfaction in innovative part particularly organizational participation. Workers work together with two or three dimensional factors for the survival and sustainability of them and enterprises through keeping relationship among superiors and subordinates over to work for well to achieve management desired goals. These are all the studies to provide base for the researcher to getting new idea and design for the present study to do the **“Go Green Model” – A Study on HRM Practices in NLC India Ltd, Neyveli.**

Source: Model Developed by Researcher

Problems that have been Focused on the Study

Organization strives for their work success with employee's spectrum of factors involved to growth and development. The management practices for their economic inclusiveness and sustainability is in the lime light technology transformation. Digitalization in business organization may lead in various forms namely - IoT, Machine Learning, Business Analytics, GHRM, Block chain and Fin Tech. It emphasis that key factors of human resource management concentrates on 'Go Green' practices in recruitment, selection and training and development process and employee engagement for outreaching the efficiency to maximum effort. In this process of streamline there are many issues negatively impact the organization. It emphasis that organizations of public enterprises of which Neyveli Lignite Corporation (NLC) Limited with Navaratna status has to go for benchmark, success and challenges in exercising the Go Green model practices in human resource particularly. On this backdrop, the researcher has undertaken the research study on 'Go Green' Model- A study on HRM practices in NLC India Limited (NLCIL). In this Context, the following research questions are framed :

- i. How to help 'Go Green' practices improve the level of employee engagement at NLC India Limited, Neyveli ?
- ii. Is there any impact of 'Go Green' practices of employee engagement in the organization ?

Research Objectives

The following are the study objectives:

1. To examine with the 'Go Green' practices to improve the level of employee engagement at NLC India Limited, Neyveli
2. To analyses the association with on 'Go Green' practices of employee engagement study organization.

Research Hypothesis

H_{01} = There is no association between demographic profile and the impact of 'Go Green' practices of employee engagement in NLC India Ltd, Neyveli.

Research Methodology Adoption and Execution of Analytical Tools

a) Sources of Data

This research paper is based on descriptive and primary and secondary data are used for the research study. The primary data collected from 24th January, 2022 to 28th February 2022 on interview schedule technique. Secondary sources include print and e-resources.

b) Techniques of Analysis

The collected data have been used for analysis with the help of statistical tools. The statistical techniques such as, percentage analysis, cross tabulation with chi-square tests and the mean score ranking method are applied.

c) Sampling Design

Using Snowball sampling technique the data of a sample population is 915 respondents through a well-structured interview schedule. The interview schedule was used different sample size of each category employee worked in NLC India Ltd, Neyveli. The category was identified by the researcher is *Executives Interview Schedule (n=348)*, *Non-Unionised Supervisor Interview Schedule (n=200)* and *Workers Interview Schedule (n=367)*. The questions of interview schedule were asked by the Executives, Non-Unionised Supervisor and Workers.

Analysis and Interpretation

a) Select Dependent Variables

This analysis considers for select demographic factors profile of the respondents' as they are; gender, age, educational qualification, experience in the field of NLC India Ltd, Neyveli.

b) Select Independent Variables

This chapter consider select 'Go Green' practices followed by the NLC India Ltd, Neyveli as follows;

Employee performance relate with 'Go Green' of Learning, Training and Development Practices in NLCIL.

c) Ranking Variables

The assigning rank by the executives, non-unionized supervisor and workmen for engagement and motivation of 'Go Green' practices followed by the NLC India Ltd, Neyveli as follows;

1. Ranking for Engagement on 'Go Green' Learning, Training and Development Practices in NLCIL
2. Ranking for Motivation on 'Go Green' Learning, Training and Development Practices in NLCIL.

a) Cross Tabulation with Chi-Square Test

Table – 1
Cross Tabulation of Gender and Satisfied with Online Selection Process

Gender		Satisfied with Online Selection Process				Total	Chi-Square
		Excited	Excellent	Good	Average		
	Male	87	418	254	16	775	.703 (NS)
	Female	17	68	52	3	140	
	Total	104	486	306	19	915	

Source: Primary Data.

S/NS: Significant / Not Significant

$H_{03(a)}$ = There is no association between Gender and Satisfied with Online Selection Process in NLC India Ltd

Table-1 makes it clear that the cross tabulation of Gender and Satisfied with Online Selection Process. The calculated value is higher than the 0.05 level and it is not significant. Hence the stated hypothesis is accepted. It implies that there is smooth understanding and awareness exists in this intension between the factor, gender and online selection base.

Table – 2
Cross Tabulation of Age and Satisfied with Online Selection Process

Age (In Years)	Satisfied with Online Selection Process				Total	Chi-Square
	Excited	Excellent	Good	Average		
Up to 35	9	46	24	2	81	.001 (S)
36-40	18	144	92	5	259	
41-45	21	88	83	6	198	
46-50	12	55	47	3	117	
51-55	11	55	22	0	88	
56-58	30	78	30	2	140	
59 and Above	3	20	8	1	32	
Total	104	486	306	19	915	

Source: Primary Data.

$H_{03(b)}$ = There is no association between Age and Satisfied with Online Selection Process

Table-2 shows that the cross tabulation of Age and Satisfied with Online Selection Process in the study organization. H_0 is rejected due to that the calculated value less than the significant level 0.05 and it is from that there is an association between age and satisfied of online process. Hence, it is concluded that there workers aware and they prefer to green practices of selective at all level of age groups.

Table – 3
Cross Tabulation of Educational Qualification and Satisfied with Online Selection Process

Educational Qualification	Satisfied with Online Selection Process				Total	Chi-Square
	Excited	Excellent	Good	Average		
Primary School	10	10	7	0	27	.000 (S)
Higher Secondary / Diploma	37	118	53	2	210	
Undergraduate	32	158	109	9	308	
Postgraduate	18	159	100	7	284	
Professional	7	41	37	1	86	
Total	104	486	306	19	915	

Source: Primary Data.

$H_{03(c)}$ = There is no association between Educational Qualification and Satisfied with Online Selection Process

Table-3 depicts that the cross tabulation of Educational Qualification and Satisfied with Online Selection Process it emphasis that determined value is less than significant value at 0.00. level it shows that null hypothesis is rejected and exhibits that there is an awareness and understanding among the factors at all categories of learners in the organization.

Table – 4
Cross Tabulation of Experience in the field of NLC and Satisfied with Online Selection Process

Experience in the field of NLC		Satisfied with Online Selection Process				Total	Chi-Square
		Excited	Excellent	Good	Average		
	Less than 5 years	35	184	88	5	312	.006 (S)
	5-10 years	50	216	174	11	451	
	11-20 years	19	71	39	1	130	
	More than 20 years above	0	15	5	2	22	
Total		104	486	306	19	915	

Source: Primary Data.

$H_{03(d)}$ = There is no association between Experience in the field of NLC and Satisfied with Online Selection Process.

Table-4 analyse that the cross tabulation of Experience and Satisfied with Online Selection Process. The stated H_0 is rejected that the computed value is 0.006 which is for behind that 0.005 level. It emphasis that the workers with different years of experience prefer with online selection technique in the study organization and also likes to go for greening environment.

Table – 5
Cross Tabulation of Grade and Satisfied with Online Selection Process

Grade in the field of NLC		Satisfied with Online Selection Process				Total	Chi-Square
		Excited	Excellent	Good	Average		
	Executives	32	208	101	7	348	.000 (S)
	Non- Unionized Supervisors	20	62	110	8	200	
	Workmen	52	216	95	4	367	
Total		104	486	306	19	915	

Source: Primary Data.

$H_{03(e)}$ = There is no association between Grade and Satisfied with Online Selection Process

Table-5 reveals that the employees of study organization are satisfied with online selection for which chi-square value is significant for and less than the 0.05 level. Hence H_0 is rejected and found that the workers at different grades are aware and likes over the method of green environment.

b) Mean Score Ranking Analysis

Table – 6
Mean Score Ranking of Engagement on Go Green Practices

	Variables	N	Mean	Rank
Valid	Celebrate team/ Individual achievements	915	4.6842	X
	Respect futures of your work/ Experience	915	4.9858	IX
	Built long term engagement of your work	915	5.2404	VIII
	Supply the right tool	915	5.2820	VII
	Given Individual Attention	915	5.5257	VI
	Provide Training and Coaching	915	5.7530	V
	Listen to your words	915	6.0918	III
	Get social relationship	915	6.3617	I
	Recognize proudly and Loyalty	915	6.3268	II
	Nature of work engagement increase company values	915	5.9093	IV

Source: Primary Data.

Table-6 denote that the Mean score rank of Engagement on Go Green the result indicates that the various stages of Engagement on Go Green Practices followed and assigning the rank by the respondent in all the three categorized employees in NLC India Ltd, Neyveli. On the basis of ultimate rank as suggested by mean score it can be concluded that get social relationship is occupying the first rank and followed by Recognize proudly and Loyalty is second rank, listen to your words is third rank. From the least of Celebrate team/Individual achievements is occupying the tenth rank.

Exhibit - 1 – Mean Score Ranking of Engagement on Go Green Practices

Source: Primary Data

Table – 7
Mean Score Ranking of Motivation on Go Green Practices

	Variables	N	Mean	Rank
Valid	Internal Motivators	915	5.7760	XIII
	External Motivators	915	6.2066	XII
	Awards & Rewards	915	6.6306	XI
	Interest of Job / work nature	915	6.7770	X
	Reorganization of Involvement/Employee self-efficiency	915	7.1322	IX
	HRM support and Responsibility	915	7.3508	VII
	Internal promotion	915	7.4820	VI
	Working hours	915	7.3410	VIII
	Avoidance of stress at work place	915	7.9038	V
	Avoid interpersonal conflict	915	8.0426	IV
	Recycling and waste management system	915	8.2787	I
	Helps in employee retention	915	8.2219	II
	Sense of responsibility towards environment	915	8.0874	III

Source: Primary Data.

Table-7 analyse that the Mean score rank of Motivation on Go Green and the result indicates that the various stages of Motivation on Go Green Practices followed and assigning the rank by the respondent in all the three categorized employees in NLC India Ltd, Neyveli. On the basis of ultimate rank as suggested by mean score it can be concluded that Recycling and waste management system is occupying the first rank and followed by Helps in employee retention is second rank, Sense of responsibility towards environment is third rank. From the least of Internal Motivators is occupying the thirteenth rank.

Exhibit - 2 – Mean Score Ranking of Motivation on Go Green Practices

Source: Primary Data

Policy for Implications and Conclusion

The following implications are outcome of the analysis and interpretation of data.

1. It was found with the help of percentage analysis that all the respondents had intellectual knowledge about the concept of green learning, training and development and related tasks in NLC India Limited. Therefore, the company should expand its green learning and related activities with full features in the coming years.
2. The result of cross-tabulation and chi-square test should be interpreted by, there is no relationship between the intention to conduct the learning program at NLC India Limited, Neyveli and the gender, age and educational qualification of the respondent. it was an integral part of Go Green contribution was due to employee dissatisfaction. So, the organization should conduct frequent orientation about the aspects of Go Green benefits to the selected employees and remove the barriers from them. This will improve employee integration and productivity.
3. Analysis of the mean score ranking of commitment to Go Green practices by the organization during the study period reveals that celebrating team/ individual achievements is ranked lowest. This shows that employee engagement is very low. Therefore, the company monitors the performance of the employees frequently and motivates them. As it is the same for motivation on Go Green Practices have there is no space of internal motivators is occupying the thirteenth rank. The organization should collaborate with the HR department to integrate employee achievements and review their innovative ideas. This will drastically improve the employee in their field.

The firm run periodic refresher training to employees and leaders about the green procedures and policies, connecting with NLC goals. The firm strictly following of Go Green practices in all aspects, as a result, employees demonstrate green behaviour leading to green organizational outcomes. At the corporate level, the firm benefits from cost advantages and improve financial performance. The firms also enjoy a positive brand image of a green employer, attract talented worker, create a green culture environment and achieve their sustainability goals. If the above steps are followed correctly, there is no doubt that the organization will be the leading company in the world in the future.

Scope for Further Research

1. Effectiveness of Green Technology Applications in HRM practices in Public Sector enterprises between Interstate – A Study
2. An Comparative study on Green Behaviour Impact on Organizational Development
3. Employees Awareness and Perception towards Green Technology in Public and Private Sectors – A Study

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